

A LOOK AT THE WORK OF JONATHAN SWIFT

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of the artistic and poetic features of the works of Jonathan Swift.

Keywords: Homer, Virgil, Aristotle, "The Battle of the Books", "The Tale of the Barrel", "The Modest Proposal", "Admonitions to the Malays", etc.

Jonathan Swift (1667–1745) was an English-Irish writer, poet and satirist, known for his sharp satirical works. His work is extensive and includes works written in various genres. "Ode to William Sancroft" (1690) and "Ode to Congreve" (1693) are Swift's earliest poetic works, both of which are dedicated to prominent figures of the time. His pamphlets and satirical works include: "The Battle of the Books" (1697) - in this pamphlet Swift satirizes supporters of ancient and modern literature. "The Tale of the Barrel" (1704) - in this satirical work, the struggle between the Catholic, Anglican and Puritan churches is depicted in a parody spirit. "The Letters of the Mootman" (1723–1724) and "A Modest Proposal" (1729) - in these pamphlets Swift sharply criticizes the social and economic problems of the Irish people. His most famous work: "Gulliver's Travels" (1726) - this novel is Swift's most famous work, in which Lemuel Gulliver's four fictional Through his travels to the country, he satirically depicted the vices of humanity and the shortcomings of society. "The Worldly Conversants" (1738) and "Admonitions to the Malays" (1745) - in these humorous works, Swift criticizes the social problems of his time. Swift's works are distinguished by their sharp satire and deep meaning. His work has remained relevant not only in his time, but also today. "The Battle of the Books" is a unique humorous work by Jonathan Swift, written in 1704 and written as a response to the literary and philosophical debates of that time. This work depicts the "battle" between the views of supporters of ancient and modern literature in

an allegorical and satirical style. The work reflects the contradiction between the value of ancient literature and the aspirations of modern literature for innovation. Swift expresses an intellectual point of view that defends the ancient literary heritage and satirizes the inadequacy of supporters of modern literature. Through the work, Swift uniquely elevates the importance of ancient knowledge and heritage in human history. In the work, ancient and modern books come to life in the Royal Library of England, and a battle begins between them. The main reason for this battle is the desire of ancient literature to maintain its place and the desire of modern literature to take this place. The characters are depicted by authors such as Homer, Virgil, Aristotle, who represent ancient literature, and Dryden, Temple, and other personal names who are supporters of modern literature.

Analysis: Allegorical style: The events of the work are expressed allegorically, and the war between the books reflects the symbolic meaning of human thought and literary evolution. This style allowed Swift to satirize the literary debates of society. The power of satire and irony:

Swift subtly satirizes the proponents of modern literature, exposing their unreasonable pride and superficial approaches. He also criticizes the sometimes overly conservative nature of the proponents of ancient literature.

The balance between ancient and modern thinking: While Swift emphasizes the necessity of ancient literature for humanity, he does not deny the positive aspects of modern literature. These views form the main philosophical basis of the work. **Uniqueness of language and style:** Swift uses a very lively and humorous language in the work. This style makes the content of the work not only interesting, but also touching. **The most famous work:** "Gulliver's Travels" (1726) is a novel by Swift, which satirically depicts the vices of humanity and the shortcomings of society through the travels of Lemuel Gulliver to four imaginary countries. "The Worldly Conversants" (1738) and "Sermons to the Malays" (1745) are humorous works in which Swift criticizes the social problems of his time. Swift's works are distinguished by their sharp

satire and deep meaning. His work has remained relevant not only in his time, but also today. "The Battle of the Books" is a unique satirical work by Jonathan Swift, written in 1704 and written as a response to the literary and philosophical debates of that time. This work depicts the "battle" between the views of supporters of ancient and modern literature in an allegorical and satirical style. The work reflects the contradiction between the value of ancient literature and the desire for innovation of modern literature. Swift expresses an intellectual point of view that defends the ancient literary heritage and satirizes the inability of supporters of modern literature to justify themselves. Through the work, Swift uniquely elevates the importance of ancient knowledge and heritage in the history of mankind. In the work, ancient and modern books come to life in the Royal Library of England, and a battle begins between them. The main reason for this battle is the desire of ancient literature to maintain its place and the desire of modern literature to occupy this place. The heroes are depicted by authors such as Homer, Virgil, Aristotle, who represent ancient literature, and Dryden, Temple, and other personal names who are supporters of modern literature.

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